

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF STUDENTS STUDYING AT DEGREE LEVEL

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Abstract:

The purpose of the paper is to determine the emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level in Vellore district of Tamilnadu. The sample comprised of 260 students studying at degree level out of these 121 male and 139 female. Emotional Intelligence Scale Constructed and Standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Dethe and Upinder Dhar.(2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow. The data so collected was analyzed using mean, SD, t-test and F-test. The findings of the study revealed that there is insignificant in the terms of values on the basis of gender, location of college, shift, UG degree, PG degree, type of management, hour of study, birth order, no of siblings and type of family towards emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.

Introduction:

Education is the main tool in the hands of man through which he enables himself to meet the various challenges of the life. It is a unique feature of human society which enables the human beings, not only to distinguish between the civilized and uncivilized, but also help them to achieve what otherwise remains unachieved. India has witnessed phenomenal development in education since independence. The overall literacy rate has gone up significantly during this period. It is the teacher with sufficient degree of mental health who can maintain the twin requisites of teaching-learning situations, healthy interactions in the classroom and healthy participation by students in lessons.

Education is the key to all processes of development especially human development. Catalytic action of education in this complex and dynamic growth process needs to be planned meticulously and executed with great sensitivity. Education is fundamental to all-round development of human potential-material and spiritual. It refines sensitivities and perceptions that contribute to national cohesion, a scientific temper and independence of mind and spirit thus furthering to goal of socialism, secularism and democracy enshrined in our constitution.

Emotional Intelligence:

Emotional Intelligence (EI) is a new area of research in the context. The growing interest in the construct of EI can be attributed to the recent theories taking broader conceptualization of intelligence. EI can be included as a member of an emerging group of potential "hot" intelligence that included social intelligence, practical intelligence, personal intelligence and emotional creativity. Each of these forms a coherent sphere that partly overlaps with EI, but separates human abilities in different ways. The various characteristics make up EI such as self motivational ability to control impulses, regulate moods and keep distress away.

"Emotional Intelligence is involved in the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of those emotions and manage them." (Mayer et al, 1999). "Emotional Intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth."

Intelligence is considered as one of the most desirable personality qualities in today's society. I.Q. tests are presently employed for many purposes such as selection, diagnosis and evaluation in all parts of society. It claims that, "it is the single most effective predictor of individual performance at school and on the job. (Andoh, 1998) Some critics of I.Q. believe that intelligence is more of a result of an individual's opportunities to learn skills and information in a particular situation. They emphasize that successful learning in school depends on many personal characteristics such as persistence, interest in school, and willingness to study. Encouragement for academic achievement received from friends, family and teachers is also important, together with other cultural factors.

Hein (2005, 2008, 2009) the mental ability we are born with which gives our emotional sensitivity and potential for emotional management skills that help us maximize our long term health, happiness and survival." Byron Stock (2007) "Emotional Intelligence (EI) is the ability to acquire and apply knowledge from your emotions and the emotions of others." You can use the information about what you're feeling to help you make effective decisions about what to say or do (or not to say or do) next.

Statement of the Problem:

The problem chosen for the study may be stated as "Emotional Intelligence of students studying at degree level.

Sample of the Study:

The sample of the present study consisted of 260 students studying at degree level. These samples are employed in Vellore district at Tamilnadu. Among these samples 121 male and 139 females. Random sampling techniques were used to draw the sample form the students at degree level.

Statistical Techniques Used:

The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, SD and “t” test to accept or reject hypotheses

Operational Definitions of Key Term Used:

Emotional Intelligence is involved in the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of those emotions and manage them.

Tool Used In the Present Study:

Emotional Intelligence Scale Constructed and Standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Detha and Upinder Dhar (2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow.

Description of the Tool:

The scale was developed by the Likert method. For scoring the scale, a score of 5,4,3,2, and 1 was given to category. The sum of the scores of all the statements constituted the total score of the scale. The maximum and minimum scores, which the students may score on EI, will be 170 and 34 respectively. There are five response categories (Strongly agree), (Agree), (Uncertain), (Disagree) and (Strongly disagree) for each of the seventy items.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out, if there is any significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to gender, location of college, shift, UG degree, PG degree, type of management, hour of study, birth order, no of siblings and type of family.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to location of college.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to shift.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in locus of control of students at degree level with respect to ug degree.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to pg degree.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to type of management.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to hour of study.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to birth order.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to no of siblings.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level with respect to type of family.

Differential Analysis for Emotional Intelligence Scores Towards Students Studying at Degree Level:

Gender and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 1: ‘t’ test values for Students Studying with Degree Level based on Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Male	121	118.33	31.54	0.629	NS
Female	139	120.73	29.79		

From the table 1, it is inferred that ‘t’ value is 0.629, which is not significant at 0.05 level as it is lesser than table value of 1.97. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and a research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that both male and female degree studying students do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.

Location of College and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 2: ‘t’ test values for of Students Studying with Degree Level based on Location of College

Location of College	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Rural	105	116.29	31.97	1.445	NS
Urban	155	121.87	29.50		

From the table 2, it is inferred that ‘t’ value is 1.445, which is not significant at 0.05 level as it is lesser than table value of 1.97. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and a research hypothesis is rejected. It is

inferred that both rural and urban degree studying students do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.

Shift and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 3: 't' test values for Students Studying with Degree Level based on Shift

Shift	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Morning	129	120.17	27.72	0.446	NS
Evening	131	118.77	32.24		

From the table 3, it is inferred that 't' value is 0.446, which is not significant at 0.05 level as it is lesser than table value of 1.97. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and a research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that both morning and evening degree studying students do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.

UG Degree and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 4: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of UG Degree Studying Students

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	248.010	124.005	2	0.132	NS
Within Groups	242035.293	941.772	257		
Total	242283.304		259		

From the Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 0.132, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of UG Degree studying students with respect to their emotional intelligence.

PG Degree and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 5: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of PG Degree Studying Students

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	163.457	81.728	2	0.087	NS
Within Groups	242119.847	942.101	257		
Total	242283.304		259		

From the Table 5, the calculated 'F' value is 0.132, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of PG Degree studying students with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Type of Management and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 6: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	41.666	20.833	2	0.022	NS
Within Groups	242241.638	942.571	257		
Total	242283.304		259		

From the Table 6, the calculated 'F' value is 0.022, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.

Hour of Study and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 7: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Hour of Study

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	560.764	280.382	2	0.298	NS
Within Groups	241722.540	940.555	257		
Total	242283.304		259		

From the Table 7, the calculated 'F' value is 0.298, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of hour of study with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.

Birth Order and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 8: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Birth Order

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	702.684	351.342	2	0.374	NS
Within Groups	241580.620	940.002	257		

Total	242283.304		259
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From the Table 8, the calculated 'F' value is 0.374, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of birth order with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.

No of Siblings and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 9: 't' test values for based on No of siblings

No of Siblings	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
1	155	118.80	30.00	0.520	NS
2	105	120.81	31.52		

From the table 9, it is inferred that 't' value is 0.520, which is not significant at 0.05 level as it is lesser than table value of 1.97. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and a research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that both one and second siblings do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.

Nature of Family and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 10: 't' test values based on Nature of Family

Nature of Family	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Nuclear	155	118.47	30.25	0.735	NS
Joint	105	121.31	31.13		

From the table 10, it is inferred that 't' value is 0.735, which is not significant at 0.05 level as it is lesser than table value of 1.97. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and a research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that both nuclear and joint family do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is inferred that both male and female degree studying students do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that both rural and urban degree studying students do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that both morning and evening degree studying students do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of UG Degree with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of PG Degree with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of hour of study with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of birth order with respect to their emotional intelligence of students studying at degree level.
- ✓ . It is inferred that both one and second siblings do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that both nuclear and joint family do not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence.

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